

ANAMNESIS OF TUBERCULOSIS PATIENTS

Date :

Number of respondents :

Patient Name :

Age :

Anamnesis

Ask for the following symptoms.

1. A depressive mood throughout the day, almost every day, indicated by either subjective reports (e.g. feelings of sadness, emptiness, hopelessness) or the observation of others e.g. being seen crying).
2. There is a noticeable decrease in interest in all pleasures, daily activities, almost every day
3. Noticeable weight loss or gain without any special effort or an almost daily decrease and increase in appetite.
4. Difficulty sleeping or sleeping excessively almost every day.
5. Psychomotor agitation or retardation almost daily (observed by others, not merely disturbing feelings of anxiety or subjective slowdown).
6. Fatigue or loss of energy almost every day.
7. Feelings of worthlessness or a marked sense of guilt
8. Decreased ability to think or concentrate, or full of indecision almost every day
9. Recurring thoughts about death (not just fear of dying), recurring thoughts about suicidal ideation with or without a clear plan, or there is a suicide attempt or a clear suicide plan.

Diagnosis :

Doctor's Name :